

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory Map excursion guidelines for Nicosia (Cyprus)

WP2 D2.2

HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursion, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

1. Define Objectives:

General Objective:

- To bring to light the significant but often overlooked contributions of women to Nicosia's historical, cultural, and social landscape through an educational and interactive city tour. This initiative aims to challenge the traditional male-centric narratives and promote a more inclusive understanding of history.

Specific Objectives:

- To identify and highlight key historical locations associated with the achievements of women in Nicosia, covering fields such as politics, education, the arts, and social reform.
- To design an engaging, experiential tour that not only conveys historical facts but also fosters critical thinking about the role of gender in shaping historical narratives.
- To create opportunities for participants to actively engage with history, using gamification and interactive elements to encourage a deeper connection with the content.
- To foster discussions around gender equality by linking historical examples of women's contributions to ongoing challenges and debates in the present.
- To ensure accessibility and inclusivity, offering the tour in formats that accommodate diverse participant needs, from physical mobility considerations to linguistic and cultural inclusiveness.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

The overarching theme of the Nicosia tour will be "A walk in the walled city of Nicosia: Women in history". The objective is to create a cohesive and engaging tour that blends thematic pillars, highlighting women's contributions to the history of Nicosia while ensuring a rich and varied experience. So, this tour can weave together **four key thematic pillars**, showcasing the interconnectedness of women's roles in shaping Nicosia:

- **Political influence and activism:** Highlight the critical roles women have played in political movements and local governance, showcasing their influence on both the island's independence and social justice efforts. This pillar will be intertwined with

stories of cultural and social reforms, illustrating how political activism has often catalyzed broader community engagement.

- **Cultural and educational achievements:** Focus on the contributions of women in literature, the arts, and education, emphasizing how these achievements have both reflected and shaped the political and social landscape of Nicosia. Participants will discover how cultural expressions often serve as a form of activism and a vehicle for social change.
- **Social reform and community leadership:** Celebrate the women who have driven social change through philanthropy, entrepreneurship, and grassroots initiatives. By integrating stories of community leadership with cultural and political narratives, participants will understand how these efforts are interrelated and essential to the fabric of Nicosia's history.
- **Everyday women as agents of change:** Acknowledge the contributions of everyday women whose efforts in families, communities, and workplaces have significantly impacted Nicosia's development. This theme will be woven throughout the tour, showing how the everyday actions of women contribute to larger historical narratives and movements.

Group composition and diversity: To enhance the experience of the tour, participants will be organized into groups with a maximum capacity of 20 individuals. The composition of these groups can take two different approaches:

1. **Diverse participant profiles:** Create groups that include a mix of students, local stakeholders, adults, and intergenerational participants. This diverse composition will foster meaningful interactions and provide a variety of perspectives, enriching discussions and insights during the tour.
2. **Specific target audiences:** Alternatively, groups can be formed based on specific demographics, such as only young people or stakeholders. This focused approach allows for a more tailored experience, enabling the blended thematic elements to resonate deeply with participants' interests and backgrounds. For example:
 - A group of young people might explore how modern activism connects with historical movements and the roles of women today.
 - A group of local stakeholders could examine historical contributions alongside current initiatives that shape Nicosia's community.

By blending these thematic pillars and defining group composition in this way, tour guides can create a rich narrative that is both engaging and relevant, allowing participants to appreciate the multifaceted contributions of women to Nicosia’s history.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

City, Country: Nicosia, Cyprus	
Number	Tour point
1	Faneromeni School
<p>Information:</p> <p>The Ottoman period in Cyprus was during 1571 – 1878. During the last decades of the Ottoman period in Cyprus, primary education began to develop in the Orthodox community of the island. Faneromeni School was founded in this context, which was the first primary school for girls in Cyprus. The school was intended for the daughters of the wealthy families of the Greek Cypriot community and was founded on the initiative of Archbishop Makarios I.</p> <p>During its first year 35 female students were studying in all six classes of the school. Twenty years later, in 1880, the school had 152 female students and it was the only school for female students in Nicosia. During its first years the classes were reading, writing, mathematics, religion classes, Greek history classes and handcraft classes. Female students learned the values that a girl should follow in order to compromise with society’s values. Such values were modesty, care, diligence and obedience.</p> <p>Back at that time, women were considered ashamed to work. Because of that, the school committee used to give scholarships to girls with fewer opportunities and from poor villages. In this way, they gave them the opportunity to be educated in order to become teachers.</p> <p>Inside Faneromeni School the first higher institution for female teachers was established back in 1903. Female teachers used to be paid less than male teachers and also, married female teachers weren’t allowed to work and they were obligated to stop working as teachers when they were planning to get married.</p> <p>The Higher institution was shut down in 1937 and the building was a part of the Pancyprian Highschool institute which welcomed only female students. In 1975, was the only year that the school was a mixed-gender school. Back then, directress and female teachers of Faneromeni School, had a crucial involvement in the development of women’s associations. One example was Theano Parouti – Liasidou, who was a directress of the school from 1887 until 1901. Later she quitted because she was about to get married, and</p>	

Eleni Christou was placed as a directress of the school. Some years later, in 1914, they managed to create a women's association in Nicosia.

In recent years Faneromeni School had a kindergarten, primary school, and high school. Now, it works as a department of the School of Architecture of the University of Cyprus.

Quiz:

What was Faneromeni School when it was created?

1. The first primary school for girls in Cyprus. [Correct answer]
2. The first school in Cyprus.
3. The first university for architects in Cyprus.

2

Anna Tigiridou

Information:

Anna Tiggidou was born in Lefkara, attended the Parthenagogeio Faneromenis, and studied dentistry at Ecole Dentaire de Paris. She became the first Cypriot dentist and upon her return to Cyprus, she opened a dental practice in Larnaca (1923-1939). During World War II, she relocated to Lefkara, where she continued her practice until the end. She participated in the Panhellenic Dental Congress in Athens (1955) and married the teacher Achilleas Michael Tiggidis from Lefkara.

Quiz:

Who was Anna Tigiridou?

1. The first teacher in Cyprus.
2. The first dentist in Cyprus. [Correct answer]
3. The first architect in Cyprus.

3

Royal Hall

Information:

The Royal Hall used to be one of the first cinemas in Nicosia until the end of the 40s. Today, the same building is being used as an event venue.

On the 25th of April 1955, the Pancyprian Protest of Female Workers took place there and the protest was about social security and for a better working environment. In the

announcement, they were mentioning the right to be absent from work when sick, the security of the widows and orphans, and equal payment between men and women.

On the 9th of July 1959, there was another crucial event in this place. The founding conference of the Pancyprian Federation of Women’s associations took place there. At this conference there were 1500 female participants from around Cyprus. This conference was about the right of vote for women, for equal rights between men and women in social and political life, for social security, for legislative security of mothers and children, for equal payment between men and women, for whole education and professional skills of children, for the security of all female workers, and for a peaceful and independent Cyprus.

Quiz:

1905 was the year women voted for the first time in elections, however...:

1. Someone neglected to write into the law that of those who paid taxes, only men were entitled to vote. [Correct answer]
2. Only women who did not work were allowed to vote.
3. Only women who were married had the right to vote.

4

Diamantou Charalambous

Information:

During the period that Cyprus was under British Colonial. Back on these years, Cyprus was a place of constant strikes and demands for change. Diamantou Charalambous was a construction worker in May 1940. This was something really revolutionary for the social norms of those years. Diamantou combatted all gender stereotypes and refused to respond to any of the gender norms that wanted women to stay in the private sphere, as good mothers, and good housewives. In May 1940 Diamantou Charalambous took part in a demonstration of unemployed construction workers in Nicosia. She was savagely beaten by the police for taking part in this demonstration, in which the workers demanded that the colonial government open jobs for the unemployed. Unfortunately, there aren’t any date for the exact place that this took place.

Quiz:

Who was Diamantou Charalambous?

1. Diamantou Charalambous was the daughter of Makarios during the British colonial period.

2. Diamantou Charalambous was a construction worker during the British colonial period. [Correct answer]
3. Diamantou Charalambous was a famous teacher during the British colonial period.

5 Arsinoes Street

Information:

The Arsinoes Street took its name from Arsinoe, a historical figure from ancient Cyprus. Arsinoe was the wife of King Leontokrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. Also known as Arsinoe II, she was the queen of Cyprus in the 3rd century BCE and had significant influence in the political and cultural affairs of that era. During her reign, she conducted numerous excavations and projects to improve Cypriot society. The street that bears her name recognizes the importance of Arsinoe in the history of Cyprus and the Ptolemaic period, while also honoring her contributions to ancient Cypriot culture.

Quiz:

Where did Arsinoes Street in Cyprus get its name from?

1. From Arsinoe, daughter of Lefkippos from Ancient Greek Mythology.
2. Arsinoes Street was named after the wife of King Leontocrates of Cyprus during the Ptolemaic dynasty. [Correct answer]
3. Arsinoes Street took its name from the president of the Republic of Cyprus, Arsinoe.

6 Ledras Street -Loukia Nikolaidou

Information:

Ledras Street is a major shopping street in central Nicosia. Around Ledras Street, Loukia Nikolaidou, the first female painter in Cyprus, had one of her first exhibitions in 1934. Loukia Nikolaidou, was the first female painter that studied Art abroad. She was born in 1909 in Limassol and died in 1994, at Penn in England. Back in the time, she decided to go abroad, in Paris and study Art.

During that time, that was a very brave decision since decisions like that were not aligned with what the society would expect from Loukia to do. Societal stereotypes and gender norms would expect Loukia to stay at home and start her own family.

She studied in Paris at the Colarossi Academy and then she continued to the School Nationale Superieure des Beaux-Arts. She came back to Cyprus in 1933, and she made her first three exhibitions, both in Nicosia and Limassol. The exhibition in Nicosia, was around

Ledras Street, the exact location is unknown. The exhibitions were in 1934, 1935 and 1936. Later on, she continued with other great and famous exhibitions both personal and in collaboration with other famous artists.

In 1992, there was an exhibition dedicated to her work at the National Gallery in Nicosia.

Quiz:

Loukia Nicolaidou was the first female painter in Cyprus. Where did she study?

1. Nicosia.
2. Paris. [Correct answer]
3. England.

4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

Complementary materials will be selected to display, such as photographs of the locations, photographs of the women, readable texts, etc.

5. Tour Excursion Planning:

For a walking tour in Nicosia from Faneromeni School to Ledras Street, participants can expect the journey to take approximately 1.5 to 2 hours, during which they will cover various historical and cultural highlights. The route is generally flat, as Nicosia is situated on the Mesaoria plains, featuring no significant inclines. This terrain is ideal for walkers of all ages, including those with mobility considerations.

Interactive Learning and Engagement

- Interactive learning activities: At each historical site, participants can engage in interactive learning experiences. These activities can include reading detailed information, watching audiovisual material that highlights the achievements of each woman represented in the tour, and participating in discussions or quizzes designed to encourage critical reflection. The goal is to move beyond passive listening; we aim to foster active engagement with the material, making history more relatable and impactful.

- Gamified elements: Incorporate gamified components by utilizing a treasure hunt mobile application. At each stop, participants can explore questions related to the featured woman's life and contributions. This engaging approach not only promotes learning but also instills a sense of exploration and adventure, encouraging participants to think critically about the legacy of each historical figure.

Narrative-based tour structure

- Chronological or thematic linking: Create a coherent narrative thread that links the various points of the tour, either chronologically or thematically. This structure should highlight the diverse contributions of women in Nicosia, allowing participants to see the connections between different historical figures and their shared impact on the city. By the end of the tour, participants should feel they have gained not just a collection of facts, but a deeper understanding of the historical forces at play and how women have navigated and influenced them.

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

The organizers should welcome the participants to download the mobile app before the implementation of the piloting tours. In this way, participants will have time to prepare themselves and the tour will be more efficient and completed based on the agreed timetable. However, a QR could be provided on the spot for the participants to engage those that might not download the app prior to the pilot tours. Regarding the content of the tours, open questions and/or multiple-choice questions could be an option in order to enhance the interaction between participants and facilitators during the tours.

2. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

Ensure that the tour is accessible to all, ensuring the equal experience to diverse audience, considering physical accessibility, language options, and cultural sensitivity. Use inclusive communication elements (language and visuals).

The tour should be adapted in a way that compromises the specific needs of participants who face different kind of challenges. For example, in cases where participants may face mobility challenges, then the tour should be accessible. The suggested tour in old Nicosia does not includes any roads/paths with difficult access for individuals with mobility difficulties. However, the facilitators should be aware that there are small roads that might challenge some individuals. To ensure accessibility at each point, facilitators are kindly encouraged to address to the National HerStory Report in order to adapt the key points of the tour based on the participants needs.

Regarding cultural sensitivity, and taking in mind that in Cyprus there are communities that they are mainly speaking English, Arabic, or French, it is highly recommended to ensure the possibility of a translator throughout the tours. In this way, the tours will assure a friendly and safe environment for interaction.

Finally, the content is easily adjustable to the participants' needs. Future facilitators are highly welcomed to encourage equal participation of all genders in the tour in order to expand the impact and diffuse the information about female footprints in history, among society.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

Following the tours' completion, it is important to collect feedback from participants. This will add on the improvement of the tours and thereby, influence the impact. Firstly, participants should be requested to complete the European Union (EU) questionnaire ([Add link](#)). Secondly, the questionnaire from the herStory project's consortium could also be diffused among the participants to receive feedback for further improvement.

4. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

Stakeholders, historians, individuals with a background on architecture, gender experts, social inclusion organisations and relevant NGOs and local authorities, could expand their own network and enhance mutual collaboration for better outcomes. Along with that, local authorities and local communities are highly recommended to participate and evolve the content through the interconnection with the local network and the benefits of such collaborations.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

The tours in Nicosia can be tailored to reflect the unique historical and social contexts of Cyprus, addressing specific periods and the interests of diverse target audiences. Emphasis can be placed on various monuments and historical sites that illustrate the contributions of women to the Labor Women's Movement and bi-communal relations. For example, a walking tour could explore the role of women in society, highlighting their paths to social mobility and their significant achievements in fostering community ties across divides. This thematic focus allows participants to discover how women's activism has shaped both local and national narratives, contributing to social change and unity in the region. By customizing excursions in this way, participants can engage more deeply with the complex history and heritage of Nicosia, gaining a nuanced understanding of the social dynamics that have influenced the island's evolution.

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

Involve tour guides that are well educated and conscious to the content and thematic of the excursion, to deliver accurate and engaging tour. In the case of self-guided tours, ensure the quality of information shared and the interactive element.

Below you can find some relevant organizations, based in Cyprus:

- Center for Gender Equality and History (KIIF): <https://kiif.com.cy/>
- Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies (MIGS): <https://medinstgenderstudies.org/>
- Fimonoi Foundation: <https://fimonoi.com/>
- POGO Women's Movement: <https://www.pogocy.com/>
- The Advisory Center for the support of the Family – SYKESO: <https://sikeso.com/>
- Center for Social Innovation – CSI Cyprus: <https://csicy.com/>
- Be an Ally Foundation: <https://beaafoundation.com/>
- RESET Cyprus: <https://resetcy.com/>
- Commissioner for Gender Equality: <https://www.institutionforgenderequality.gov.cy/>
- National Machinery for Gender Equality: <https://www.gov.cy/mjpo/tomeas-dioikisis-kai-isotitas-ton-fylon-2/monada-isotitas-ton-fylon/>

Extra tips.

Having a QRCode printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

2. Documentation and templates

The deliverables of WP4 activities are presented below:

D4.1 HerStory Map pilot implementation

- **Invitation/ agenda/ program:** A template will be shared by KEAN.
- **Signed attendance list**
- **Mintes/ report (tbd)**
- **Other evidence** (in case of pictures we need consent forms)